

How Chinese Expatriates Transformational Leadership affect the Employees Performance: mediating and moderating roles

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Abstract:

The study investigated how Chinese expatriates Transformational Leadership to local people affect staff performance, evaluation roles, and rating, and the relationship between change leadership and job performance and organizational behavior. The researcher assessed the participatory role of the work through the organization's work ethic and cultural intelligence. It is also a necessary role for African labor values through labor performance with the OCB. The investigator sampled 300 staff members and 20 guards. 2 questionnaires used for data collection. The information was coded, filtered, and uploaded to SPSS. Correlation analysis, regression analysis, Andrew F. Hayes 3.4 procedure, and Sobel test are used to answer the hypothesis. The results of this study suggested that there is a linear relationship that exists between transformation leadership and performance. Also, change leadership had an indirect relationship with organizational cultural practices.

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1.1 Introduction

Because of the importance of frontline staff performance in a competitive world, experts have tried to find its forecasts. Among the various variants that have been researched in the literature, previous research has shown that participation plays a key role in improving the performance of employees in services - and in services provided to individuals. The success of an organization depends largely on the role of management (Terglav et al., 2016). Thus, managers influence the attitudes, behaviors and behaviors of employees (Avolio et al., 2004). Also, the way they communicate with customers (Wallace et al., 2013). Specifically, transitional leadership, defined as "a style of leadership that transforms followers into superiority by changing their behavior, motivates them to do better than originally expected" (Pieterse et al., 2010), has now embraced paradigm in leadership literature (Judge and Piccolo, 2004) .

Previous studies in the leadership field provide strong evidence for the positive effects of this flexibility on the performance of frontline staff (Fuller et al., 1996; Judge and Piccolo, 2004; Lowe et al., 1996). However, further research is needed regarding the specific mechanisms by which these effects occur, as well as the conditions for limitations in which change leadership improves staff performance (Holten et al., 2018; PanandLin, 2015; PatiarandWang, 2016). Therefore, this study aims to provide new information on why and under what circumstances dynamic leadership enhances the performance of early employees, including job performance and organizational behavior directed at the organization (OCBO), in the context of the tourism and tourism industry.

1.2 Theoretical background of the study

In today's organizational structure and culture there is a significant impact on the leadership and culture of the organization, under this sociological research study (Robbins 2003), which describes the three stages of social interaction including pre-arrival, interaction and metamorphic, this process proves to contribute to in the end the decisions remain with the organization. The pre-arrival stage finds each person coming with a set of values, attitudes, and expectations of work and meeting. One major goal of a business school, for example, is to enable business students to integrate ethics and ethical business firms. The ideological views of leadership styles by Fielder, (2010), which influence the work force in an organization, are the literary intentions that describe the history of a strong leader such as Napoleon, Mao, Churchill, Roosevelt Reagan, which he has always described in terms of human nature. . Leadership ideas thus focus on their own merits and demerits, leaders such as South Africa's Nelson Mandela and Apple founder Steve Jobs, and American expression expression chairman Steve

1.3 Overview of the Study in South Sudan

The study was conducted in South Sudan's investment companies, which were established in 2011. The investigation includes Dar Petroleum Operating Company, (DPOC), SUDD Petroleum Company and Greater Pioneer (GPOC) companies with more than 15000 employees. All the companies had 16 departmental ratings including project, management, engineering, procurement, Accounts and Finance, Aviation, Treasury, Insurance and Sales, Human Resources and Operations departments. These investment companies operating in South Sudan have their branches in the oil fields n Paloch in Block A, B, and Tharjak in Unity province.

1.4 Significance of the study

In response to these calls for further research, this study demonstrates the concept of who can identify (SIT) and the concept of social exchange (SET) to determine the role played by

the psychological relationship between an employee and an organization, according to organizational identification and participation in the work. The study also examined whether changing leadership affected followers' performance and made them more and more involved in their role by improving their level of participation. In addition, we investigate whether the relationship between transformation leadership and performance can be aligned in the order of organizational calling and activity involvement. Also, this study investigates the conditions of limitations that can balance the relationship between transformation leadership and trade union identification and involvement in work. While managers and their leadership styles are an important determinant of employee performance, early employee qualities, such as their personality traits, are also needed in shaping their attitude and the influence of followers' behavior.

1.5 Research questions

The quality of the research output will depend on the research questions. This study will find the answer to the following questions; (1) How is China's changing leadership bringing about a change in the functioning and conduct of the organization? (2) How does the Transformational leadership make limited adjustments for directors and cultural intelligence? (3) How does a dynamic leadership shape the Participatory and Performance Work of an organization? (4) How does involvement in work involve the relationship between change leadership and employee performance? (5) How did the African work enhance the working relationship between the OCB and the OCB?

1.6 Objectives of the study

This study aims to achieve the role of transformational leadership in the two performance outcomes of employees: (1) Performance and organizational ethics. In addition, follow-up, this study aims to explore the effects of Transformation leadership mediation on co-operation, performance, and Organization Citizenship Behavior. Furthermore, the balanced effect of revolutionary leadership on expatriate's transformation and intelligence of cultural organization. Finally, the balanced role of African labor values in the performance of jobs and in the conduct of a cultural organization.

1.7 Contribution to the study

This study provides several contributions to the academic literature and managerial practice. First, it responds to additional research calls examining interventions that explain how change leadership can affect employee performance, (Pan and Lin, 2015; Patiar and Wang, 2016). In particular, it investigates the effects of two-way mediation: organizational identification and participatory involvement. Second, as noted by Walumbwa and Hartnell, (2011), limited research has examined whether multiple mediators are successively the result of leadership in employee performance. Therefore, in order to address this gap, the study also examined whether both identifying the organization and participating in the work were part of the relationship. This study provides important and useful information in leadership transformation literature. Third, as recently noted by Lu et al., (2018, p. 187). In current research of organization and management, one of the main tasks is to create conditions for the boundaries of a particular belief or subject. However, to our knowledge, no previous studies have investigated whether active personality enhances the effects of transformational leadership. Therefore, in view of the critical role of active humanity, this study enriches our understanding of the conditions under which dynamic leadership influences the performance of employees under it. Finally, the results of this study allow organizations to gain an understanding of why and under what circumstances employees act in this way, enabling them to make informed decisions about their personnel management strategies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The effect of transformational leadership on job performance and OCBO

Previous research has linked change leadership to various organizational outcomes. In this study, we focus on five performance outcomes: job performance, job involvement, preparation of expatriates, Cultural Intelligence and OCBO. Job's work is an important organizational benefit to the leadership of reform. Organizational Behavior (OCB) symbolizes "the practical, personal performance of a person, which can be directly recognized through a well-organized reward system and in combination, promotes effective and efficient organizational performance" (Organ, 1988, p. 4). In particular, this study examines OCBOs (Williams and Anderson, 1991), values that benefit the organization as a whole. OCBOs are closely related to different approaches to organizational success, such as productivity and profitability and customer satisfaction (Podsakoff, et al., 2009). Therefore, it is important to examine these behaviors in the oil industry in South Sudan.

In this study, we show that organizational identification is one of the key ways in which transformation leaders influence the workforce in OCBO. Transformation leadership has been suggested as affecting the identification of followers with the group (Tse and Chiu, 2014) and the identification of relationships (Liang, et al., 2017), "which is how one defines oneself by following the leader and the role of the relationship" (Sluss and Ashforth, 2007, p. 32). That a review of technical studies by Van Knippenberg, et al., (2004) explains the importance of the concept of self-identity and identity is formed in understanding how leadership influences the behavior of followers.

2.2 Transformational/charismatic leadership and organizational culture

Intensive research on change leadership / culture and organizational organization has provided evidence of a link between a certain sizes of culture and change / leadership leadership (Box 2). In particular, Block (2003) when examining leadership-cultural interactions found that employees who measured their managers quickly at the top of a leadership change were more likely to see their organization's culture as engaging, integrating, flexible, and mission-focused. In a study of 32 units of a large financial institution, Xenikou and Simosi (2006) showed that the transformative leadership style and culture of personalized culture had a negative impact on the performance of business units through a culture of achievement. Overall, the question that has recently received some attention in relevant research involves the relationship between the particular size of the organisation's culture and leadership / transformational changes.

2.3 Leadership as an antecedent of organizational culture

According to Berson, et al., (2008) findings provided practical application of the hypothesis that the process by which senior employees work relates to the outcomes of an organization including different levels of organizational culture. Specifically, they found that CEOs 'prices are indirectly related to business performance through organizational culture. In another study of senior and middle management executives Tsui, Zhang, Lang, Xin, and Wu (2006) found that leadership had a profound impact on the organisation's culture. Their findings highlighted that cultural values are developed over time through the interaction of members with institutional processes or are done in a short period of time as a result of deliberate church actions. Some socholars said that the combination of leadership changes and high-level business leadership predicts highly predictable cultures with a sense of reward.

2.4 The mediating effect of cultural orientations in the leadership-organizational outcomes link

In the context of experimenting with leadership as a solution to organizational culture, there have, recently, been a large number of empowering studies examining how different cultural practices interact as mediators in the link between leadership styles and organizational outcomes, such as performance, employee commitment, organizational identification, and innovation (Chong, et al. , 2018; Elenkov & Manev, 2005; Lok, Westwood, & Crawford, 2005; Ogbonna & Harris, 2000; Simosi & Xenikou, 2010; Xenikou, 2017). The mediating effect of organizational culture on the link between leadership styles and organizational focus outcomes is strongly supported in many studies. Research on the impact of cultural mediation has examined and provided evidence of a shared effect on organizational size, leadership styles in organizational performance, innovation, employee commitment, and organizational identification, This issue is particularly important because the clearly competitive combination of values and beliefs, such as cooperation and personal development, is systematically emphasized in the organization's effective functioning (Quinn, 1988; Miron, Erez, & Naveh, 2004; Hartnell, et al., 2011; Hartnell, et al. , 2016;).

2.5 Transformational Leadership and Work Engagement

The choice of members as to when they will be fully present and engaged in the work is made up of internal (eg rational intentions and sense of security) and external (e.g., availability of resources) (Kahn, 1992). Through these things, leaders can influence how followers choose to be present (not to be physically present) and get involved. In addition, emphasizing the importance of goals, similar to role models (House & Shamir, 1993), revolutionary leaders invest all their money in achieving these goals. House and Shamir (1993), added that the leaders of the revolution raised the unique value of achieving the goals and encouraged the commitment of the followers, attaining a sense of purpose in the goals. Therefore, both the influence created and the motivation motivation can lead members to believe that the combined goals are meaningful (e.g. psychological) and achievable, and are more willing to present themselves physically, mentally and emotionally at work. Therefore, this study assumes that revolutionary leaders provide comprehensive and integrated goals for followers and make them believe that these goals have a purpose. In short, the study expects that with the above behaviors described above, revolutionary leaders can encourage their members to become more involved in what they do. Previous research (e.g. Chua & Ayoko, 2019; Ghadi, et al., 2013; Vila-Vázquez, et al., 2018; W. Zhu, et al., 2009) suggests that revolutionary leaders improve the performance of members on these issues to a greater extent.

2.6 The mediating role of work engagement

We suggest that active participation plays a role in the balance between change leadership and job creation and OCBO. Further research shows a positive relationship between change leadership and employee involvement (e.g. Macey and Schneider, 2008). As noted earlier, revolutionary leaders inspire and mentally stimulate their workers. They also use deals and show individual consideration by paying attention to the needs of their employees (Bass, 1990). Based on the SET, former employees may feel compelled to reimburse these methods for higher levels of involvement. Previous empirical studies support this relationship (e.g. Salanova, et al., 2011; Zhu, et al., 2009). In their research diary, Tims, et al., (2011) and Breevaart, et al., (2014) found a positive relationship between daily leadership fluctuations and daily employee engagement. Similarly, Ghadi, et al., (2013) and Kopperud, et al., (2014) have confirmed that flexible leadership strongly influences the level of employee involvement. The researcher also said that the employees involved performed better and showed OCBO. When employees are involved they provide their resources (e.g. cognitive,

emotional, and physical) to the roles of the work, thus contributing to the goals of the organization (Rich, et al., 2010). Therefore, the employees involved are “active in their work for a long time, more attentive and more focused on responsibilities, and more involved in the activities that build their role” (Rich, et al., 2010, p. 620). Therefore, it is very likely that they will respond well to customer requests and demonstrate better performance. The sum, based on the above assumptions, suggests that job involvement directs the relationship between change leadership and job performance and OCBO.

2.7 The moderating effect of proactive personality

Previous research has provided a complete review of practical personality literature. For example, using work success as a framework, Fuller and Marler, (2009) reported in their meta-analysis that active personality is related to the purpose and success of a high-quality career, work ethic, constructive motivation, practical behavior, and diversity related to motivation and flexibility, among others. Similarly, a meta-analysis conducted by Thomas, et al., (2010) revealed significant connections between active personality and work performance, active organizational commitment, job satisfaction and social interaction. In a previous study he also investigated the link between active personality and leadership (e.g. Deluga, 1998). Second, as noted by Thomas, et al., (2010), the recognition of employees in anticipation of their ability to change their environment can have a profound effect on “understanding and feeling involved in their organizational environment” (Thomas, et al., 2010, p. 279). Finally, working employees who change their work environment are more likely to be more active in their work (Bateman and Crant, 1993) and, therefore, more involved (Dikkers, et al., 2010; Ghorbannejad and Esakhani, 2016; Hakanen, et al., 2008; Li, et al., 2017).

2.8 Expatriate Adjustment

It is very difficult to adapt to a new work environment with new cultures and diversity. According to Peltokorpi & Froese, (2012), research on expatriate correction for culturally correct performance is growing. He suggests that rebels who fail to practice their traditional values often get cut off. According to Black, (1990) Cultural adjustment of the cross is the transformation of an individual or family into a natural need. In addition, mental health or knowledge of a new environment is important, (Black, 1990, p.). According to Takeuchi, et al., (2002), there are three distinct aspects of adjustment to be considered when analyzing expatriate health: (a) adjustments to the normal living environment in foreign culture, (b) adjustments in job expectations and roles, and (c) adjustments communication practices and hosting customs. Takeuchi, et al., (2002) surveyed 215 Japanese immigrants, married men working in the United States in various industries. In conclusion, the correction of deviant culture was significant in the consequences of dismissal. In addition, this study has shown that the adjustment to the culture of living abroad is related to normal health satisfaction and job-related satisfaction. Also, the low levels of satisfaction reported were related to the larger goals of early termination of assignments (Takeuchi, et al., 2002). Major repairs can be influenced by other external repair items, namely; job satisfaction, home-language language fluctuations, previous travel and work, Type of work, help-seeking assistance, cultural intelligence, and general cultural distance.

2.9 Work values

The literature work values are represented by an encyclopedia of definitions (Steyn & Kotze, 2004). Wils, Saba, Waxin, and Labelle (2011) argue that this lack of a complete and imperfect combination of theorization in relation to the stated structure. Thus, Wong and Yuen (2015, p. 31), quoting Ros, Schwartz and Surikiss (1999), pointed out that 'work values' is a term used to describe feelings, attitudes and beliefs held in relation to general work, and specifically

different types of work, in addition to of certain factors, such as respect, pay, job security, and workplace.

2.10 Relationship between work values and job performance

Lyons et al. (2006) found that performance values define job performance and job selection. In other words, performance values affect performance in the workplace, including performance. Liu et al., (2006) examined members of the pyramid-selling networks and found that better alignment of labor values at all hierarchical levels leads to better performance. Chou (2007) suggested that if teachers were able to recognize the values of their school, they would be committed, and school performance would improve as a result. Wang and Kao, (2009) examined entry-level police and found that organizational commitment has a positive impact on mediating work ethic and performance. Therefore, this study found that the employment rates of workers in the green energy industry have an impact on their working conditions and performance in the workplace.

2.11 African Work Values

In traditional Africa, laziness is not encouraged. The people of Africa are mostly farmers and fishermen. But there were also experts such as male medicine, rain makers, kings and priests, diners, potters, blacksmiths Nihinlola, (n.d), and other technologies. Whatever the job, it is important for the person to be involved. African Work values are reflected in hard work, segregation of workers, social work, Respect for the elderly, Social work, the importance of rest.

2.12 African Traditional Work Values in the Light of Decent Work

The yard used is for the purpose of the High Performance Agenda and includes the following: Job Creation is an economy that creates opportunities for investment, business, skills development, job creation and a healthy living. A comparative analysis of Decent Work expectations and traditional African values can be drawn below:

Table 1: Responsible employment objectives vs ethics of non-discriminatory African labor employment

Decent Work	Traditional African Work Ethics
Creating Jobs	Traditional Africa has a lot of jobs to offer. A child is actually born into his or her parent's vocation, perfects the skills, grows up in it and probably passes it down to his/her posterity .
Extending social protection	Safety, adequate free time and rest, consideration for family and social value and traditional health care are made available for workers.
Promoting social dialogue	This is the role of guilds and trade union such as the Agbekoya Parapo.
Guaranteeing fundamental Rights at work	Though African society is mostly patriarchal in nature, the values of personal human dignity and sense of social justice helps guides them in the care for the disadvantaged or poor workers.

2.13 Conceptual Framework of the study

The vision of revolutionary leadership has inspired a number of research experts in the field of organizational leadership over the decades. The idea was introduced by Burns in 1978 and developed by Bass (1985) and others (Bass & Avolio, 1994). According to (Rich et al., 2010) when employees are engaged to be married, they give of their time to work and to achieve the goals of the organization. Karate et al., (2014), suggested that the organization's organizational behavior depends on the involvement of the work. Thus, the conceptual framework emphasizes the relationship between flexibility, and mental meditation is mentioned afterwards.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

Source: Research findings

Hypothesis:

- H1. Transformational leadership has a positive effect on task performance in an organization.
 H2. Transformational leadership has a positive effect on organizational citizenship behaviors.
 H3. Transformational leadership mediates work engagement with the task performance and organizational citizenship behaviors.
 H4. Transformational leadership has a moderating relationship between expatriate's adjustment and cultural intelligence.
 H5. Work engagement mediates a positive relationship between task performance and OCB.
 H6. African work values moderate the relationship between task performance and OCB

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The research design of this study is celebrated - it is consistent in design. This is because the purpose of research is to establish a relationship between independent and trustworthy diversity. Responsibility discussion was used to verify the information contained in the questionnaire.

3.2 Sample and data collection

To test the proposed hypotheses, the researcher took a vigorous study with the staff of previous companies. The population was extracted from Chinese oil companies operating in South Sudan. The number of people surveyed was made up of (300) low-level staff and (20) their directors. Two sets of questions were published. Information relating to the leadership of change, employee involvement, traveler reform, cultural intelligence and African work values demanded by workers while performance information was collected from directors. After the purpose of the study was explained, respondents were asked to answer questions that indicated the companies they worked for. They were confirmed anonymously. Using a purposeful sampling method, the Companies were selected based on their Chinese ownership and operating in large oil companies in South Sudan. The crew list was collected in stores and

all odd numbers were sampled. Where the sample size is not reached, the process is repeated until the required number is reached. Behavioral procedures were followed by seeking the consent of each participant before any questionnaire was submitted. Therefore, data were collected from several respondents in a one-time survey.

3.3 Common method bias assessment

As the information was obtained from individual respondents in a one-time study, the researcher examined the selection in a well-used manner. We have used both non-invasive methods to control common possible mechanisms (Podsakoff et al., 2003). By considering the procedures followed, respondents were reassured that they were confidential about the anonymity of the information provided. This reduces the likelihood that employees will respond to dishonesty (Podsakoff et al., 2003).

4. DATA ANALYSIS, PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Demographic information (Supervisors)

Performance was evaluated by a total of 20 managers. As a result, 85% of the directors were male, 60% of whom belonged to other religions and the rest of them were Christians or Muslims. Male directors make up 80% of the management. Most directors (90%) were married and most (85%) had a bachelor's degree. The majorities of 50% managers are in their 40s to 50s and have worked for 10 to 14 years with their companies as shown in Table 3 below.

Table 1: Demographic information of respondents

Demographic Factor	Subordinates		Supervisor		
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
Gender	Male	249	83.6%	17	85%
	Female	49	16.4%	3	15%
Religion	Christian	289	97.6%	6	30%
	Moslem	7	2.4%	2	10%
	Others			12	60%
Marital status	Married	18	6.5%	18	90%
	Never married	253	91.0%	1	5%
	Divorced	7	2.5%	1	5%
	Widowed	0	0.0%	0	0%
Highest education level	Junior secondary school	1	0.3%	0	0%
	Senior secondary school	28	9.7%	0	0%
	Diploma	104	36.0%	0	0%
	Bachelor Degree	122	42.2%	17	85%
	Master's Degree	34	11.8%	3	15%
Age	15-28	16	5.4%	0	0%
	29-39	144	48.8%	8	40%
	40-50	133	45.1%	10	50%
	51-61	2	0.7%	2	10%
	62-72	0	0.0%	0	0%
Working period	1-4	147	49.3%	0	0%
	5-9	78	26.1%	4	20%
	10-14	47	15.7%	12	60%
	15 and above	27	9.0%	2	10%

4.2 Reliability

This study assessed the reliability of internal consistency and initial validity of the tools, shown in Tables 4 and 5 below. The Cronbach alpha test was used to test the reliability of the questions. The researcher examined the entire list of questions and the internal variability of the trust. Cronbach's initial values for the entire questionnaire were 99%. Cronbach's alpha testing was conducted with a variety of groups including transformation leadership, human involvement, cultural participation, work participation, cultural intelligence, African work values, and performance. Initially, the effect of each variation ranged from 0.24 to 0.99. However, after the deregulation of the Cronbach alpha low scores, the score reached between 0.69 and 0.99 which is reliably revised.

Table 4: Overall Cronbach alpha reliability score

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.956	63

Table 5: Individual items Cronbach alpha reliability score Reliability Statistics

Items	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha
Transformational leadership	27	0.99
Expatriates Engagement	20	0.81
Organization Citizenship Behavior	10	0.89
Work engagement	9	0.96
Cultural Intelligence	10	0.69
African Work Values	20	0.98
Task performance	18	0.72

4.3 Test of normal distribution using descriptive analysis

Descriptive statistical analyzes were performed on each individual variance in order to spread the common distribution of small, high, mean and standard deviations. From the table below, the lowest and highest values show from 1 low to 5 high as shown in table 6 below. This means that distribution is normal.

Table 6: Normal distribution test using descriptive statistical method

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
TL	300	1.46	5.00	4.4972	.71410
EA	296	2.74	5.00	4.2346	.50891
OCB	296	3	5	4.25	.428
WE	296	1	5	4.21	.532
CI	300	2.75	4.86	4.1379	.36542
TP	165	3.10	4.80	4.1661	.18396
Valid N (list wise)	165				

4.4 Factor analysis

Evaluation analysis (EFA) is used in the Principle component Analysis analysis center to assess the authenticity of the instruments. Research based on 0.5 large loads to accept the validity of research tools. Sample size of 300 is confirmed by the use of this method. As shown in Table 2, part of the EFA results in the table below indicated that the tested variables were TL (Transformative leadership), EA (Expatriates changes), OCB (Cultural Behavior), WE (Participatory Activity), AVW (African work rates) and TP (work performance) uploaded over 0.5. Of the 86 items prior to factor analysis, 8 items were removed because they were not properly loaded. The remaining items uploaded more than 0.5 in line with the recommendations of the SmarPLS Manual (Hair et al., 2016). The results are shown in Table 7 below.

Table 7: Exploratory factor analysis Component Matrix^a output result using PCA

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
T1	Has a clear understanding of where we are going	.736							
T2	Paints an interesting picture of the future for others	.904							
T3	is always seeking new opportunities	.833							
T4	Paints an interesting picture of the future for others	.940							
T5	Inspires others with his/her plans for the future	.936							
T6	Paints an interesting picture of the future for others	.934							
T7	Is able to get others committed to his /her dreams	.873							
T8	Leads by doing other than simply telling	.677							
T9	Leads by example	.763							
T10	Fosters collaboration among	.938							
T11	Encourages employees to be team players	.913							
T12	gets the others to work for others for the same goal	.902							
T13	Develops a team attitude and spirit among employees	.771							
T14	shows coworkers that he/she expects a lot from them	.827							
T15	Insists on only the best performance	.894							
T16	will not settle for less	.913							
T17	Acts without considering the feelings of others	.774							
T18	Shows respect for personal feelings of others	.900							
T19	behaves in a manner thoughtful of others personal feelings	.846							
T20	Treats others without considering their personal feelings	.757							
T21	Challenges others to think about old problems in a new ways	.850							
T22	Asks questions that prompt others to think to think	.830							
T23	has stimulated me to rethink the way others think	.924							
T24	has ideas that have challenged others to reexamine some of my basic assumptions about their work	.891							

T25	Challenges others to think about old problems in a new ways	.861						
T26	asks questions that prompt others to think	.898						
T27	has stimulated me to rethink the way others think	.899						
E13	I am sure I can deal with the stresses of adjusting to a culture that is new to me	-.706						
OCB2	A man should feel a sense of pride in his work	.925						
OCB3	Having a good job makes a person worthy of praise from his friends and family	.907						
OCB4	Work enables one to contribute to the welfare of others	.763						
OCB8	A good work should pay well and enable one to have the things he/she wants	-.843						

4.5 Relationship between variables using Pearson correlation

Pearson integration was performed to determine the relationship between subject variability. Coelation fitation of +1 to -1 with a P value of less than 0.05 is considered significant. As shown in Table 8 below, on the other hand, there is a negative relationship between TL (leadership leadership) and expatriates involvement (B = 00.135, P = 0.02), and, negatively correlates between leadership leadership and organizational behavior (B = - 204, P = 0.000). In addition, the negative relationship between change leadership and job involvement (B = 00.168, P = 0.04), and performance performance (B = 1160, P = 008). On the other hand, there was a statistically significant positive relationship between change leadership and cultural intelligence (B = 0.922, P = 0.000), and African Work values (B = 0.89, P = 0.000). In addition, expatriates adjustment has a positive statistical relationship with Organization behavior (B = 0.191, P = 0.001), user engagement adjustment (B = 0.290, P = 0.000), expatriates engagement and Task performance (B = 0.193, P = 0.01). However, there was a statistically negative correlation between adjustment of expatriates and African Work values (B = 00.116, P = 0.46). also, there was a negative relationship between expatriate reform and cultural intelligence but nonetheless, it is not statistically significant. In addition, the OCB had a positive statistical relationship with activity involvement (B = 0.510, P = 0.000), and job performance (B = 0.671, P = 0.000). However, a statistically negative relationship with Cultural Intelligence (B = 00.189, P = 0.000) and African Work involvement. In addition, participation in the workplace has a positive statistically significant relationship with job performance (B = 0.681, P = 0.000), but a negative statistical relationship with cultural intelligence (B = 00.181, P = 0.006) and African Work Values (B = 00.193 , P = 0.001). According to the results in the table below, Fine Arts also has a positive statistical relationship with African Work values (B = 0.854, P = 0.000) and a negative statistical relationship with Task performance (B = 00.163, P = 0.014). In addition, the number of African jobs has a negative statistical relationship with job performance (B = - 0.162, P = 0.007) as shown in the table below. This result tests the exit of hypothesis 1 and hypothesis 2. At the same time, H1: Transformation leadership has a positive effect on the performance of the tasks being instructed. The results show that there is a negative relationship between leadership change and job performance. (B = 1160, P = 008). This means that with the development of the transformation leadership, there is a decline in job performance and vice versa. Also, research H2; Transformation leadership has a positive relationship with organizational and cultural values and is also rejected as a result of the merger. The results show that there is a link between leadership change and organizational behavior. (B = 20204,

P = 0.000). Thus, with advances in transformation leadership, there is a decline in organizational ethics and vice versa.

Table 2: showing Pearson Correlations between the variables

		TL	EA	OCB	WE	CI	AWV	TP
TL	Pearson Correlation	1						
	Sig. (2-tailed)							
	N	300						
EA	Pearson Correlation	-.135*	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.021						
	N	296	296					
OCB	Pearson Correlation	-.204**	.191**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.001					
	N	291	291	291				
WE	Pearson Correlation	-.168**	.290**	.510**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004	.000	.000				
	N	296	296	291	296			
CI	Pearson Correlation	.922**	-.020	-.189**	-.181**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.761	.004	.006			
	N	236	233	232	233	236		
AWV	Pearson Correlation	.894**	-.116*	-.215**	-.193**	.854**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.046	.000	.001	.000		
	N	300	296	291	296	236	300	
TP	Pearson Correlation	-.160**	.193**	.671**	.681**	-.163*	-.162**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.008	.001	.000	.000	.014	.007	
	N	274	273	270	273	227	274	274

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

TL (Transformational Leadership, EA (Expatriates adjustment), OCB (Organizational Cultural Intelligence), WE (Work engagement, CI (Cultural Intelligence), AWV(African Work Values), TP(Task Performance).

4.6 Regression analysis

As shown in Table 9 below, a retrospective review process was conducted to ensure the strength of the relationship between transformation leadership and job performance and transformation leadership and organizational behavior following analysis. As a result, there is a statistically weak relationship between transformation leadership and performance (B = 00.160, P = 0.008). Also, there is a weak statistically weak relationship between the transformation leadership and the cultural behavior of the organization (B = 00.204, P = 0.000). This result confirms the relationship analysis. Therefore, the effects of hypothesis; H1: Transformation leadership has a positive relationship with the performance of functions in the organization is rejected. Also, H2: Transformation leadership has a positive relationship with the cultural wisdom of the organization being disciplined.

Table 9: Regression analysis between transformational leadership and task performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.684	.189		24.754	.000
	TL	-.111	.041	-.160	-2.674	.008

a. Dependent Variable: TP
TP(Task Performance)

Table 10: Regression analysis between transformational leadership and organizational cultural behavior

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.866	.177		27.447	.000
	TL	-.138	.039	-.204	-3.537	.000

a. Dependent Variable: OCB
OCB (Organizational Cultural Behavior)

4.7 Hypothesis 3: Transformational leadership mediates between work engagement, task performance, and Organizational cultural behavior.

Mediation analysis using process 3.1.4 is also done to determine the effect of mediation leadership on changes in the relationship between active participation, performance, and organizational behavior. Also, the Sobel test using quantpsy.org was used to validate the results of the analysis (Aroian, 1944/1947) first; the researcher used transformational leadership as a manager, job involvement as a covariate, work performance and organizational behavior as a participatory approach. As a result, there was a good relationship between performance and organizational ethics. ($b = .616$, $t(267) = 9.296$, $P = .000$). Moreover, job performance and job involvement did not have a significant relationship with change leadership, (X predictive M: $b = .10$, $t(267) = 1.112$, $P = .267$). Also, transformation leadership did not have a significant impact on the morale of the organization's culture when it was at another level in the performance of the task. (M Predictability Y (method b): $b = -.080$, $t(266) = -1.809$, $P = .072$). However, job performance has had a significant impact on organizational culture (X predicting Y c': $b = .607$, $t(266) = -.771$, $P = .000$). In the end, the indirect effect showed that there was no mediation effect of the leadership relationship between involvement in work, performance, and ethical organization because the level of confidence was zero. Also, Sobel tests confirmed that there were no significant interventions, (Sobel Aroian) test = $t = 0.862$, $P = 0.388$). (Aroian, 1944/1947). Thus, hypothesis 3: dynamic leadership associates the relationship between active participation and organizational cultural wisdom is rejected.

4.8 Hypothesis 4: Work engagement mediates the positive relationship between task performance and organizational cultural intelligence

To determine the mediation relationship between performance and the ethical conduct of the organization, the procedure 3.4.1 by Andrew F. Hayes was applied. Also, the Sobel test (Aroian test) using quantpsy.org is used to test the value of t value in concluding the result (Aroian, 1944/1947). In the first step, the functional and ethical relationships of the cultural organization were important. ($b = 0.73$, $t(267) = 14.82$, $P < .01$). The next step predicted the relationship between performing tasks in a job engagement. As a result, operational

performance had a significant positive relationship with the OCB. Also, as job engagement improves job performance it also improves. Additional measures predicted relationships where performance and work involvement were at the same level as the OCB. As a result, when job engagement and performance were at the same level, OCB had a positive relationship with job involvement, ($b = 0.2$, $t(114.5) = 2.47$, $P < 0.01$) and, also in job performance ($b = 0.6$, $t(114.9) = 9.29$, $P = 0.03$). This means that with an improved level of engagement and performance, the OCB is also improving. Therefore, based on 0.11 , $SE = 0.09$, 95% CI $[0.16, 0.25]$, and Sobel test analyzes, ($t = 2.43$, $P = 0.014$), mediated interaction relationships between performance and OCB (Aroian, 1944/1947). Therefore, the analysis failed to refute Hypothesis 5: Involvement in the workplace is linked to a good working and working relationship with the OCB

1: X variant predicts Y-Path C

X predictive Y: Path C: $b = 0.73$, $t(267) = 14.82$, $P < 0.01$

2. Various X predicts M-Path a

X predicts M: WAY a: $b = 0.7$, $t(268) = 15.15$, $P < 0.01$

3. X and m predict predict y

M Y-way prediction b: $b = 0.2$, $t(114.5) = 2.47$, $P < 0.01$

X-predicting Y-path c': $b = 0.6$, $t(114.9) = 9.29$, $P = 0.03$

4. Indirect = 0.11 , $SE = 0.09$, 95% CI $[-0.16, 0.25]$ slightly greater than zero

5. Sobel Testing: $t = 2.43$, $P = 0.014$ Result is important, mediation has taken place

4.9 Hypothesis 4: Transformational leadership moderates the relationship between expatriate's adjustment and Cultural Intelligence

In order to perform the moderation, the researcher used a straightforward order by guessing the cultural wisdom from the evolution of the arrival of leaders and the leadership of the changes as shown in Tables 12 and 13 below. The aim is to determine whether there is a significant effect or change in which the existing flexibility (change of leadership) does not exist or does not exist as stated by (Elite research 2013). The researcher ran a retrieval model to determine the amount of variance by the predictor (Conversion setting) with or without the interaction of the change leadership. The tables below show that in addition to the active word (change leadership * Tool adjustment), model 1 does not make sense $F = (2.230) = 653.5$, $P = 0.00$ while with a valid name (Transformational leadership * expatriates changes), model 2 is important $F = (3.229) = 434.4$, $P = 0.00$

Therefore, the model summary below shows that model 2 and the interaction between change leadership and integration mean more significant differences than expatriate change and expatriate adjustment themselves by R per square change = 0.850 , $P = 0.000$). Therefore, this suggests that there may be an important measure of co-operative equity in regulating the performance of work and the wisdom of the art culture.

Table 11: ANOVA tests for models 1 and 2

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	137.038	2	68.519	653.511	.000 ^b
	Residual	24.115	230	.105		
	Total	161.152	232			
2	Regression	137.065	3	45.688	434.362	.000 ^c
	Residual	24.087	229	.105		
	Total	161.152	232			

a. Dependent Variable: CI

b. Predictors: (Constant), EA, TL

c. Predictors: (Constant), EA, TL, TLXEA

CI (Cultural Intelligence), EA (Expatriates Adjustment), TL (Transformational Leadership), TLXEA (Transformational leadership interaction with Expatriates engagement)

Table 12: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. of Estimate	Error Change Statistics					
					the R Square F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	F Change	
1	.922 ^a	.850	.849	.32380	.850	653.511	2	230	.000	
2	.922 ^b	.851	.849	.32432	.000	.261	1	229	.610	

a. Predictors: (Constant), EA, TL

b. Predictors: (Constant), EA, TL, TLXEA

EA (Expatriates Adjustment), TL (Transformational Leadership), TLXEA (Transformational leadership interaction with Expatriates engagement)

4.10 Moderation effect of transformational leadership on expatriate's adjustment and cultural intelligence

To test the hypothesis that cultural intelligence in an organization is influenced by the correction and leadership of change or when changing leadership removes the relationship between boys' involvement and cultural behavior. The link between leadership for change and human engagement through cultural intelligence was assessed using the return model Andrew F. Hayes 3.1.4. Visual effects of the conditional impact of X on Y were used to edit the graph below. The results below show that as leadership change and expatriate reform improve, cultural intelligence improves. Where expatriate's change leadership and reform is a bad thing, cultural intellect is not poor. Therefore;

H4: Transformation leadership has a balanced relationship with expatriate's and Cultural intelligence = failed to refuse

Figure 2: Evaluating changing leadership relationships through expatriate's and intelligence reforms and culture

4.11 Hypothesis 6: African Work Values Moderating Task performance and Organizational Cultural Behavior

Linear regression analysis was performed to determine the difference between a model and a link (African work values x performance) and another model without a link as shown in Table 14 below. Analysis reveals that by linking factors, the relationship between performance and organizational behavior is more important $F(2, 267) = 114.1, P < 0.01$. And with the variability of available communication not available, there is a correlation between the performance of tasks and the behavior of the traditional ethical system $F(3, 268) = 78.5, P < 0.01$. Therefore, the summary table below shows that there is an important account for the variability of the correlation between African labor and employment values and the OCB rather than African labor prices and performance as specific OCB items. The change of R^2 first model = .461, $P < 0.01$ while the first model is $R^2 = 0.009$. This means that it could result in a balance between the African values in the performance and functioning of the organisation's culture.

Table 13: ANOVAa

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	28.676	2	14.338	114.053	.000 ^b
	Residual	33.566	267	.126		
	Total	62.242	269			
2	Regression	29.222	3	9.741	78.471	.000 ^c
	Residual	33.019	266	.124		
	Total	62.242	269			

a. Dependent Variable: OCB

b. Predictors: (Constant), AWV, TP

c. Predictors: (Constant), AWV, TP, AWVXTP

OCB (Organizational Cultural Behavior), AWV (African Work Values), TP(Task Performance), AWVXTP (African Work values interaction with Task performance)

Table 14: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	F
1	.679 ^a	.461	.457	.355	.461	114.053	2	267	.000	
	.685 ^b	.469	.464	.352	.009	4.401	1	266	.037	

dictors: (Constant), AWV, TP

dictors: (Constant), AWV, TP, AWVXTP

(African Work Values), TP(Task Performance), AWVXTP (African Work values interaction Task performance)

est the notion that African work measures the state of the relationship between work ormandance and organizational behavior, Andrew F. Hayes' method 3.4.1 was used to test measurement effect. The visual output data of the X-Y conditions was used to determine relationship between moderation (African cultural value), X -variable (performance), and riable (organizational cultural intelligence). The figure below shows that, as African labor s and job losses decline for the poor, the organisation's morale is deteriorating. As an cultural values and performance improve, the organisation's ethics are improving. In s of the poor performance of the African workforce, the performance of the jobs was the e and was equally equitable and fair.

refore;

(H6): African labor value has a moderate effect on job performance and OCB = failed to be rejected.

Figure 3: The measure of the value of the African work ethic in the operations and conduct of a cultural organization

4.12 Qualitative Data

What is the culture of work? Respondents were asked what they understood about work culture. The majority of respondents reported that the job was defined as the fulfillment of tasks assigned to you by a senior person.

Employment Benefits: According to respondents, employees benefit from work by earning money, training given to employees, promotions, communication with others and understanding of other people's cultures. Others have reported that they benefit by paying their children's school fees and improving their family and children's lives.

Differences between industrial and traditional work: Responses defined industrial work as a form of technology-related work. Respondents provided examples such as technology, payment function, and overtime work. While respondents described traditional work as a form of work it was performed by activities performed by the local community. Examples such as working without pay, position, working for free time.

The contribution of immigrants to the company: according to interviewees, Chinese expatriates conducting research and development. In addition, they provide jobs in South Sudanese by hiring people. In addition, they help with field lessons. Also, they advise on health issues in the organization. In addition, respondents reported that Chinese exiles help advice technical engineers on how to develop their career plans. Finally, Chinese retailers also offer technical advice on global marketing strategies and advise on oil product prices.

5.1 Conclusion

This study examines how China's transformation leadership in the local community affects the performance of workers: the role of mediation and balancing engagement and performance OCB companies in South Sudan. Current research has explored the positive and strengthening link between leadership performance and organizational and cultural (OCB) ethics. In addition, this study examined the effect of a change in leadership between active participation and organizational behavior. Although local workers have acknowledged that Chinese kidnappers exercise excellent leadership in oil companies, the researcher found that there is a negative link between leadership transformation and performance. Also, change leadership had an indirect relationship with organizational cultural practices. In addition, it was also found that change leadership does not have a significant effect on participation in the work and cultural ethics of the organization and in the work of the Work. Further, the researcher found that dynamic leadership implicates the relationship between traveler refinement and cultural ingenuity. As a result, whenever there was progress in the revolutionary leadership, there was progress in the transformation of the Sudanese cultural intellectual and cultural discourse in the South Sudanese oil companies. In addition, the researcher found that active participation contributes to a positive relationship with the performance and performance of the organization and the behavior of the organization. Finally, it was found that African work measured the relationship between performance and the OCB. Therefore, whenever the values of African work were strong, there was an improvement in the intellectual capacity of the organization.

5.2 Recommendation

Based on the results of the study, the researcher recommends that Chinese refugees should keep in mind that as revolutionary leadership has proven to be a very effective research tool, it can also be an effective tool in reducing innovation and innovation among workers. Moreover, the use of revolutionary leadership in the context of South Sudan shows that African working values should not be expected immediately but gradually. Therefore, Chinese

exiles should gradually engage Sudanese mindsets in embracing the doctrines of revolutionary leadership.

5.3 Limitation:

The researcher recommends further research into South Sudanese involvement in the acquisition of new skills, the balanced role of African work values, and Cultural intelligence.

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